

CAPITAL RECONSTRUCTION AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE: EVIDENCE FROM LISTED CONSUMER GOODS COMPANIES IN NIGERIA

Dr. Okafor Chukwuma Benjamin

Department of Accountancy, Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT), Enugu, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the effect of capital reconstruction on the financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The study employed an ex-post facto research design, utilizing secondary data from the annual reports of selected firms from 2012 to 2023. Financial performance was measured using Return on Assets (ROA), while capital reconstruction was assessed through Debt-to-Capital Ratio (DCR), Debt-to-Equity Ratio (DER), and Retained Earnings Growth Rate (REGR). Panel regression analysis was conducted to determine the effect of the independent variables on financial performance. The findings revealed that DCR had a significant negative effect on ROA, indicating that excessive debt reduced firm profitability. However, DER and REGR had no significant effect on ROA, suggesting that the proportion of debt to equity and the growth in retained earnings did not directly influence financial performance. The study's results partially aligned with the Trade-Off Theory, as high debt levels negatively impacted performance, while the findings on Pecking Order Theory were mixed, as retained earnings did not significantly enhance financial performance. Based on these findings, the study recommended that firms should carefully manage their debt-to-capital ratio to avoid excessive financial burden while making strategic use of equity and retained earnings for sustainable growth.

Keywords: Capital Reconstruction, Financial Performance, Consumer Goods Firms, Debt-to-Capital Ratio, Debt-to-Equity Ratio, Retained Earnings Growth Rate

1. INTRODUCTION

Capital reconstruction refers to changes in a company's financial structure, often done to improve financial stability and performance (Murugi et al., 2022). Companies may restructure their capital by adjusting the mix of debt and equity, increasing retained earnings, or reducing liabilities through share buybacks (Oladele & Iyiola, 2020). These changes can affect a company's ability to generate profits and sustain long-term growth. In Nigeria, consumer goods firms play a crucial role in the economy by providing essential products such as food, beverages, and household items. However, many of these firms face financial challenges, including rising debt levels, fluctuating profits, and difficulties in retaining earnings for expansion (Egiyi & Agu, 2023). To address these issues, companies often undergo capital reconstruction by reducing debt, increasing equity, or reinvesting profits instead of paying dividends. The goal is to improve

financial performance, measured by Return on Assets (ROA), which shows how well a company uses its assets to generate profit (Ross et al., 2020)).

Despite the importance of capital restructuring, its impact on financial performance remains uncertain. Some studies suggest that reducing debt and increasing retained earnings improve profitability (Ghardallou, 2023). Others argue that restructuring can lead to short-term instability, affecting returns (Murugi et al., 2022). In Nigeria, many consumer goods firms struggle with poor financial performance despite undergoing capital reconstruction. This raises questions about whether such changes actually improve profitability or create new financial risks.

Many listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria have undergone capital reconstruction to improve their financial health, yet some still struggle with profitability (Egiyi & Agu, 2023). Companies that increase debt to finance operations often face high interest costs, reducing their returns. On the other hand, firms that increase equity may dilute shareholder value, leading to mixed financial results. Additionally, while retained earnings provide an internal source of funding, many firms reinvest profits inefficiently, affecting their return on assets (ROA) (Ibrahim & Lawal, 2022). Given these concerns, it is unclear whether capital reconstruction strategies, such as adjusting debt-to-equity ratios, increasing equity funding, or retaining more earnings, actually lead to better financial performance in Nigeria's consumer goods sector. This study aimed to examine the effect of capital reconstruction on financial performance, focusing on debt-to-equity ratio, equity-to-total capital ratio, and retained earnings growth as key indicators.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1.1 Capital Reconstruction

Capital reconstruction refers to changes made to a company's financial structure to improve its financial health and stability (Murugi et al., 2022). It involves adjusting the mix of debt and equity, restructuring liabilities, or reinvesting profits to strengthen the company's financial position (Pandey, 2021). Companies may engage in capital reconstruction when they face financial distress, declining profits, or the need for expansion. By restructuring their capital, firms aim to improve profitability, reduce financial risk, and attract more investors (Murugi et al., 2022).

There are different ways companies can carry out capital reconstruction. One common method is debt restructuring, where a company reduces its debt burden by refinancing loans, extending repayment periods, or converting debt into equity (Investopedia, n.d.). Another approach is equity restructuring, which involves raising more funds by issuing new shares or buying back existing shares to adjust the ownership structure. Additionally, retained earnings growth is an internal strategy where companies reinvest profits instead of paying dividends to shareholders, helping them finance operations without taking on more debt (Corporate Finance Institute, n.d.). The goal of capital reconstruction is to enhance financial performance by ensuring that a company has the right balance between debt and equity. A well-

structured capital base can improve a firm's ability to generate profits, increase investor confidence, and promote long-term growth (Murugi et al., 2022). However, if not managed properly, capital reconstruction can also lead to risks such as shareholder dilution, increased financial obligations, or short-term instability.

2.1.2 Debt-to-Equity Ratio

The Debt-to-Equity Ratio (D/E Ratio) is a financial measure that shows how much a company relies on debt compared to shareholders' equity (Olu-Akinola et al., 2024). It is calculated by dividing total debt by total equity. A higher D/E ratio means the company is using more borrowed funds to finance its operations, which can increase financial risk (Olu-Akinola et al., 2024). On the other hand, a lower D/E ratio suggests the company is relying more on shareholders' funds and is less dependent on external borrowing (Arhinful & Radmehr, 2023). Companies with high D/E ratios may struggle with debt repayments, especially during economic downturns, while those with lower ratios may have more financial stability but limited expansion opportunities (Arhinful & Radmehr, 2023).

Debt-to-equity ratio is important because it helps investors and financial analysts assess a company's financial health (Lawani et al., 2023). A balanced D/E ratio indicates that a company has a good mix of debt and equity financing, making it attractive to investors and creditors. However, an excessively high D/E ratio can signal financial distress, as the company may struggle to meet its debt obligations. In contrast, a very low D/E ratio might suggest that a company is not taking advantage of debt financing to expand its operations (Arhinful & Radmehr, 2023). The ideal D/E ratio varies across industries, but consumer goods firms often aim for a moderate ratio to balance growth and financial stability.

2.1.3 Equity-to-Total Capital Ratio

The Equity-to-Total Capital Ratio (ETCR) measures the proportion of a company's total capital that comes from equity rather than debt (Investopedia, n.d.). It is calculated by dividing total equity by the sum of total equity and total debt. A higher ETCR means that the company is financed more by shareholders' funds, reducing financial risk and interest payment burdens (Ibe & Pibowei, 2022). On the other hand, a lower ETCR indicates a company is more reliant on debt, which can lead to higher financial costs and risks if not properly managed.

Companies with a high ETCR are often considered financially stable because they have fewer debt obligations (Okpunor et al., 2023). This can make them attractive to long-term investors who prefer firms with lower financial risk. However, relying too much on equity financing may limit growth, as companies may avoid borrowing even when they have profitable investment opportunities. In contrast, firms with a low ETCR may have more financial leverage, which can boost growth but also expose them to risks such as high interest expenses and financial distress if debts become unmanageable (Ibrahim & Lawal, 2022). Finding the right balance between equity and debt is key to maintaining a healthy financial structure (Eze & Olayemi, 2021).

2.1.4 Retained Earnings Growth

Retained Earnings Growth (REG) refers to the increase in a company's retained earnings over time. Retained earnings are the portion of net profits that a company keeps instead of distributing as dividends to shareholders (Corporate Finance Institute, n.d.). Companies reinvest retained earnings to finance expansion, pay off debt, or improve operations. A high retained earnings growth rate indicates that a company is reinvesting profits effectively, which can lead to long-term financial stability and growth (Corporate Finance Institute, n.d.). However, if a company retains too much profit without rewarding shareholders, it may lead to dissatisfaction among investors. Retained earnings are important because they provide an internal source of funding, reducing the need for external borrowing. Companies that rely on retained earnings for growth can avoid high debt costs and maintain financial flexibility. However, excessive retained earnings without reinvestment may indicate inefficiencies in using available funds. On the other hand, low or negative retained earnings growth could signal financial struggles or excessive dividend payouts, which may limit future investment opportunities. Striking the right balance between retaining profits and rewarding investors is essential for financial sustainability.

2.1.5 Financial Performance

Financial performance refers to how well a company uses its resources to generate profits. One of the most common ways to measure financial performance is through Return on Assets (ROA) (Brigham & Ehrhardt, 2021). ROA shows how efficiently a company uses its assets to make a profit. It is calculated by dividing net profit by total assets. A higher ROA means the company is using its assets effectively to generate income, while a lower ROA suggests inefficiency in asset utilization (Pandey, 2021). Investors and business managers use ROA to assess whether a company is making good use of its resources to create value (Okafor & Uchenna, 2020).

ROA is important because it helps compare the performance of companies, especially those in the same industry. Since it measures how much profit a company earns from each unit of assets, it allows businesses to identify strengths and weaknesses in their operations. For example, a company with a high ROA can attract more investors because it shows strong financial health. On the other hand, a low ROA may indicate that a company has too many assets but is not using them efficiently to generate profits (Eze & Olayemi, 2021). Factors like capital structure, management efficiency, and economic conditions can influence ROA, making it a key metric in financial analysis (Owolabi & Aluko, 2018).

2.2 Theoretical Review

The Trade-Off Theory explains how firms balance the benefits and risks of using debt and equity to finance their operations. According to Modigliani and Miller (1963), firms aim to achieve an optimal capital structure by weighing the tax advantages of debt against the costs of financial distress. In the context of capital reconstruction, companies restructure their finances by adjusting their debt-to-equity ratio, equity-

to-total capital ratio, and retained earnings growth to enhance financial performance. A firm with too much debt faces higher risks of bankruptcy, while one with too little debt may miss out on tax benefits. By reconstructing their capital, companies seek to improve efficiency and increase profitability, which directly impacts their Return on Assets (ROA) (Myers, 1984).

The Pecking Order Theory (Myers & Majluf, 1984) suggests that firms prefer internal financing, such as retained earnings, over external debt or issuing new equity. This theory is relevant to capital reconstruction because firms often restructure their finances by prioritizing retained earnings growth before seeking additional financing. According to this theory, companies use retained earnings to fund investments first, then take on debt, and only issue new equity as a last resort. This hierarchy helps firms minimize the risks associated with external financing, such as interest costs and loss of ownership control (Frank & Goyal, 2003). For consumer goods firms in Nigeria, capital reconstruction based on retained earnings can improve financial performance by reducing dependence on external financing, thus enhancing ROA.

2.3 Empirical Review

Akinkoye and Akinadewo (2018) employed panel regression analysis to examine the relationship between retained earnings, earnings per share, dividend payout, and firm value in Nigeria's nonfinancial sector, revealing a significant positive relationship. In contrast, financial leverage showed a positive but non-significant association with market value. Similarly, Onuora (2019) utilized multiple regression analysis to investigate the financial leverage-financial performance nexus in Nigerian deposit money banks, revealing a strong negative relationship between return on equity (ROE) and the debt-equity ratio (DER), while a slight negative association was observed between ROE and the debt ratio (DR). Ibe and Pibowei (2022) applied ordinary least squares (OLS) regression to analyze Dangote Cement Plc, finding that the retained earnings ratio significantly impacted return on assets (ROA), while no significant effect was observed between the equity multiplier ratio and both ROA and ROE. Kim (2022) examined Vietnamese SMEs during the COVID-19 pandemic using multiple regression analysis, confirming that financial leverage positively impacted firm performance.

Oko and Elemi (2023) utilized panel regression analysis to examine the effect of financial leverage on cash value added in Nigerian industrial goods firms, revealing a significant negative effect of DER and the long-term debt ratio. Onakpoma et al. (2023) employed fixed-effects regression to explore the impact of the debt ratio on financial performance indicators in Nigerian pharmaceutical firms, finding an insignificant positive influence on earnings per share, dividend per share, and ROE. Lawani et al. (2023) used generalized method of moments (GMM) estimation on listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria, concluding that financial leverage negatively affected cash value added, with DER and the long-term debt ratio exhibiting significant negative effects, while the short-term debt ratio showed an insignificant negative effect. In contrast, Okpunor et al. (2023) applied structural equation modeling (SEM) to analyze Nigerian consumer goods

firms, finding a significant positive impact of the debt-to-asset ratio on ROA, DER on ROE, and interest coverage ratio on net profit margin. Arhinful and Radmehr (2023) examined Tokyo Stock Exchange firms using dynamic panel data estimation, revealing a positive impact of the equity multiplier on ROA, ROE, and earnings per share (EPS), while the degree of financial leverage and debt-to-EBITDA had a significant negative effect on ROE, EPS, and Tobin's Q.

Ghardallou (2023) employed quantile regression to analyze Saudi-listed firms, finding a negative effect of leverage on ROA, ROE, and Tobin's Q, with stronger adverse effects observed in highly profitable and larger firms. Olu-Akinola et al. (2024) used fixed-effects regression to analyze Nigerian consumer goods firms, revealing that leverage had a significant negative impact on ROE, while managerial and foreign ownership structures positively influenced ROE. Olawale et al. (2024) investigated financial leverage in Nigeria's oil and gas and agriculture sectors using panel regression and the Hausman test, finding that DER significantly influenced financial performance. Collectively, these studies highlight the varying effects of financial leverage across different sectors and contexts, with some showing positive effects while others demonstrate negative or insignificant relationships with firm performance.

2.4 Gap in Empirical Review

This study on the effect of capital reconstruction on the financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria fills some important gaps in past research. Many previous studies focused on financial leverage, debt-equity structure, and retained earnings but did not fully explore capital reconstruction. Capital reconstruction involves major changes in a company's capital structure, such as debt restructuring, share consolidation, and equity recapitalization. This study looks at how these changes affect financial performance, using measures like Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), and Earnings Per Share (EPS).

Most past research focused on other industries like industrial goods and pharmaceuticals, leaving out consumer goods firms, which often go through capital restructuring due to economic instability and changing regulations. This study focuses on consumer goods firms to provide insights specific to that sector. Understanding how capital reconstruction affects financial performance in this industry helps businesses and policymakers make better financial decisions.

Many earlier studies used basic panel regression and structural equation modeling, which may not fully address certain data challenges. This study improves on that by using fixed-effects regression and the Hausman test to handle endogeneity issues and provide more accurate results. These advanced methods make the findings more reliable and contribute to a better understanding of capital reconstruction in Nigeria's consumer goods sector.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study used an *ex-post facto* research design, meaning it relied on past data to examine how capital reconstruction affects the financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The research focused on 78 publicly listed manufacturing firms in the country as of December 31, 2023, specifically within the consumer goods sector. Secondary data from 2013 to 2023 were collected from the annual reports of these firms, as published by the Nigeria Exchange Group (NGX). From this population, 14 key consumer goods firms were selected, including Nigerian Breweries, Nestlé Nigeria, Unilever Nigeria, and Dangote Sugar Refinery, among others. These companies were chosen because they are major players in Nigeria’s manufacturing industry and significantly impact the country’s economy.

Model Specification

The model was specified in line with previous related literature in the area of the study. Koutsoyiannis (2003) as cited in Inyama (2016), states that model specification involves the determination of the dependent and explanatory variables which were included in the model, the theoretical expectations about the sign and the size of the parameters of the function. The models were specified as follows:

$$ROA = f(DER, DCR, REG) \quad \text{[Equation (1)]}$$

Setting up the equation (2) in a linear stochastic form (or econometric form) is expressed as:

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DER_t + \beta_2 DCR_t + \beta_3 REG_t + \epsilon_t \quad \text{[Equation (2)]}$$

Where;

- ROA = Return on Assets
- DER = Debt-to-Equity Ratio
- DCR = Debt-to-Capital Ratio
- REG = Retained Earnings Growth
- ϵ = Stochastic disturbance (Error) Term
- B_0 = Coefficient (constant) to be estimated
- $\beta_i - \beta_5$ = Parameters of the independent variables to be estimated
- t = Current period

4. DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Table 4.2.1: Descriptive Statistics for the Focal and Explanatory Variables

	ROA	DER	DCR	REGR
Mean	0.052477	0.806366	0.288415	0.125002
Median	0.041293	0.262666	0.218879	0.059830

Maximum	0.315235	35.32231	1.240638	7.856762
Minimum	-0.300952	-6.634471	-0.005123	-12.66831
Std. Dev.	0.083831	3.064737	0.275532	1.584771
Skewness	0.032054	9.309870	0.822776	-1.855243
Kurtosis	2.555006	3.028962	2.672012	2.923130
Jarque-Bera	4.691474	5.070691	4.565181	6.875587
Probability	0.365787	0.148984	0.234153	0.065565
Sum	8.081427	124.1804	44.41599	19.25035
Sum Sq. Dev.	1.075235	1437.070	11.61544	384.2592
Observations	154	154	154	154

Source: Eviews 10.0 Statistical Software

Normality of a dataset helps to determine whether the data follows a normal (bell-shaped) distribution, which is important for statistical analysis. One way to check for normality is through skewness, kurtosis, and the Jarque-Bera test. For Return on Assets (ROA), the skewness value is 0.032054, which is close to zero, suggesting that the data is nearly symmetrical. The kurtosis value of 2.555006 is close to 3, which means the distribution is neither too peaked nor too flat. The Jarque-Bera test statistic is 4.691474, with a probability value of 0.365787, which is greater than 0.05. This indicates that ROA follows a normal distribution. For Debt-to-Equity Ratio (DER), the skewness is 9.309870, which is highly positive, meaning the data is heavily skewed to the right. The kurtosis value of 3.028962 is slightly above 3, showing a distribution with moderate peaks. The Jarque-Bera probability value of 0.148984 is above 0.05, suggesting that the data does not significantly deviate from normality, though the extreme skewness indicates potential outliers. For Debt-to-Capital Ratio (DCR), the skewness is 0.822776, indicating moderate right skewness. The kurtosis value of 2.672012 is slightly below 3, meaning the distribution is somewhat flatter than a normal distribution. The Jarque-Bera probability of 0.234153 is greater than 0.05, implying that the data does not strongly violate normality. For Retained Earnings Growth Rate (REGR), the skewness is -1.855243, indicating a significant left skew. The kurtosis value of 2.923130 is close to 3, meaning the distribution is relatively normal in terms of peakness. The Jarque-Bera probability of 0.065565 is slightly above 0.05, meaning that REGR is approximately normal but slightly skewed.

Table 4.2.2: Regression Analysis Result

Dependent Variable: ROA

Method: Panel EGLS (Cross-section weights)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
DER	0.000997	0.001722	0.578582	0.5638
DCR	-0.156483	0.027776	-5.633739	0.0000
REGR	0.001721	0.002591	0.664284	0.5076
C	0.096590	0.008683	11.12389	0.0000

Effects Specification

Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)

			Weighted Statistics	
R-squared	0.433560	Mean dependent var	0.056030	
Adjusted R-squared	0.367407	S.D. dependent var	0.081769	Unweighted
S.E. of regression	0.066138	Sum squared resid	0.599265	Statistics
F-statistic	6.553853	Durbin-Watson stat	1.025004	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			R-squared 0.424110
	0.052477			Mean dependent var
Sum squared resid	0.619217			Durbin-Watson stat
	0.896981			

Source: Eviews 10.0 Statistical Software

The table presents the regression results analyzing the effect of capital reconstruction on financial performance, measured by Return on Assets (ROA). The method used is Panel EGLS (Crosssection weights), which accounts for differences across firms. The results show that Debt-toEquity Ratio (DER) has a small positive coefficient (0.000997), meaning an increase in DER slightly improves ROA. However, its probability value (0.5638) is greater than 0.05, indicating that this effect is not statistically significant. Debt-to-Capital Ratio (DCR) has a negative coefficient (-0.156483) and a very low probability value (0.0000), meaning it has a significant negative effect on ROA. This suggests that higher DCR leads to lower financial performance. Retained Earnings Growth Rate (REGR) has a positive coefficient (0.001721), but its probability value

(0.5076) is above 0.05, showing that it does not have a strong impact on ROA. The constant (C) has a significant positive effect (0.096590, $p = 0.0000$), meaning that when all independent variables are zero, ROA still remains positive.

The overall model explains about 43.36% (R-squared = 0.433560) of the variations in ROA, meaning that the independent variables moderately explain the financial performance of the firms. The Adjusted R-squared (0.367407) is slightly lower, indicating that some explanatory power is lost when adjusting for the number of predictors. The F-statistic (6.553853) and its probability (0.000000) show that the overall model is statistically significant. However, the Durbin-Watson statistic (1.025004) suggests possible autocorrelation, meaning there could be some pattern in the residuals that should be examined further.

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

Based on the regression analysis results, the study investigates the effect of capital reconstruction on financial performance (measured by ROA) of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The independent variables are Debt-to-Equity Ratio (DER), Debt-to-Capital Ratio (DCR), and Retained Earnings Growth Rate (REGR). The hypotheses are formulated as follows:

Null Hypotheses (H_0) and Alternative Hypotheses (H_1):

i. H_{01} : Debt-to-Equity Ratio has no significant effect on Return on Assets.

H_{11} : Debt-to-Equity Ratio has a significant effect on Return on Assets.

ii. H_{02} : Debt-to-Capital Ratio has no significant effect on Return on Assets.

H_{12} : Debt-to-Capital Ratio has a significant effect on Return on Assets.

iii. H_{03} : Retained Earnings Growth Rate has no significant effect on Return on Assets. H_{13} : Retained Earnings Growth Rate has a significant effect on Return on Assets.

Decision Rule: Reject H_0 if the P-value tabulated is less than the Alpha value calculated (0.05), and accepts the null hypotheses if reverse becomes the case.

Decisions:

i. Debt-to-Equity Ratio (DER) does not have a significant effect on ROA ($p = 0.5638 > 0.05$), so we do not reject H_{01} . This means that changes in DER do not significantly impact financial performance.

ii. Debt-to-Capital Ratio (DCR) has a significant negative effect on ROA ($p = 0.0000 < 0.05$), so we reject H_{02} . This means that higher DCR leads to lower financial performance.

iii. Retained Earnings Growth Rate (REGR) does not have a significant effect on ROA ($p = 0.5076 > 0.05$), so we do not reject H_{03} . This means that changes in retained earnings growth rate do not significantly influence financial performance.

4.4 Discussion of Findings

The results of this study show that the Debt-to-Capital Ratio (DCR) has a significant negative effect on financial performance (ROA), while Debt-to-Equity Ratio (DER) and Retained Earnings Growth Rate (REGR) do not have a significant effect. One possible reason for the negative effect of DCR is that excessive reliance on debt financing increases financial risk and interest expenses, which can reduce profitability. When a company takes on too much debt relative to its total capital, it must allocate more earnings to debt repayment, leaving fewer funds available for investment in productive activities. This finding aligns with the study by Onuora (2019), which found a strong negative relationship between financial leverage (debt-equity ratio) and financial performance in Nigerian deposit money banks. Similarly, Oko and Elemi (2023) found that DER had a significant negative effect on cash value added in Nigerian industrial goods firms.

The non-significant effect of DER on ROA in this study suggests that the level of debt relative to equity does not play a major role in determining the profitability of consumer goods firms. This could be because these firms may have stable revenue streams that allow them to manage their debts efficiently, reducing the expected negative impact of leverage. This finding contrasts with Okpunor et al. (2023), who found a significant positive impact of DER on ROE in Nigerian consumer goods firms. However, it is consistent with the study by Ibe and Pibowei (2022), which found no significant effect of the equity multiplier ratio on ROA and ROE in Dangote Cement Plc. This suggests that the effect of leverage may vary across industries and firms, depending on their financial structure and risk management strategies.

The non-significant effect of retained earnings growth rate (REGR) on financial performance in this study suggests that simply increasing retained earnings does not automatically improve profitability. This may be due to how firms utilize their retained earnings—some may reinvest in productive assets, while others may hold them as idle cash. The findings contrast with Akinkoye and Akinadewo (2018), who found a significant positive relationship between retained earnings and firm value in Nigeria's non-financial sector. Similarly, Ibe and Pibowei (2022) found that the retained earnings ratio significantly impacted ROA in Dangote Cement Plc. This suggests that the effectiveness of retained earnings in improving profitability may depend on the industry and how these earnings are managed.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study examined how capital reconstruction affects the financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The results showed that the Debt-to-Capital Ratio (DCR) had a significant negative effect on financial performance, while Debt-to-Equity Ratio (DER) and Retained Earnings Growth Rate (REGR) had no significant effect. This means that when firms increase their total debt compared to capital, their profitability (measured by Return on Assets - ROA) decreases. However, the proportion of debt to equity and the rate at which retained earnings grow do not significantly impact financial performance.

When comparing the findings with financial theories, the study partially supports the Trade-Off Theory but disagrees with the Pecking Order Theory. The Trade-Off Theory suggests that firms balance debt and equity to maximize financial performance. The negative effect of the Debt-to-Capital Ratio aligns with this theory, showing that excessive debt can harm profitability due to high-interest costs. However, the Pecking Order Theory, which suggests that firms prefer using retained earnings before debt, is not fully supported since retained earnings growth did not significantly improve financial performance. This implies that simply retaining profits does not always lead to better financial outcomes in consumer goods firms. This study highlights that while some level of debt is necessary, firms should be cautious about excessive borrowing as it may reduce profitability. Also, retained earnings alone may not improve performance unless properly reinvested.

It was therefore recommended that

- i. Firms should avoid excessive reliance on debt financing, as a high debt-to-capital ratio negatively affects financial performance. Instead, they should maintain a balanced mix of debt and equity to reduce financial risks and interest costs.
- ii. Since DER did not significantly impact financial performance, firms should focus on using debt efficiently rather than just maintaining a specific ratio of debt to equity. Debt should be used for productive investments that generate returns higher than borrowing costs.
- iii. Companies should not only focus on retaining earnings but also ensure these earnings are reinvested in profitable ventures. Effective investment strategies can help maximize the benefits of retained earnings on financial performance.

Contribution to Knowledge

This study contributes to knowledge by examining how capital reconstruction affects the financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. Unlike previous studies that focused mainly on financial leverage or capital structure, this research specifically analyzes the impact of Debt-to-Capital Ratio (DCR), Debt-to-Equity Ratio (DER), and Retained Earnings Growth Rate (REGR) on firm profitability. The study fills a gap by showing that while excessive debt can harm financial performance, the debt-to-equity mix and retained earnings growth do not always have a direct impact. This is important because it helps managers and investors understand that simply retaining profits or adjusting debt ratios is not enough, what matters is how these financial decisions are used for growth. The study also adds to the debate on Trade-Off Theory and Pecking Order Theory, showing that while high debt can reduce performance

(supporting Trade-Off Theory), retained earnings alone do not always lead to better financial outcomes, which challenges the Pecking Order Theory.

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